

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF GROWTH, BODY LINEAR MEASUREMENTS AND SERUM ALKALINE PHOSPHATASE OF MALE AND FEMALE BROILER LINES IN SHIKA, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study was conducted to genetically evaluate the performance of male and female broiler lines in National Animal Production Research Institute (NAPRI). Data on body weight and body linear measurements were obtained from 350 progenies consisting of 100 birds each for sire and dam line and 75 birds each for sire control and dam control respectively. The growth and body linear measurements traits considered were body weight (BW), body length (BL), Body girth (BG), Thigh length (TL), keel length (KL) and Shank length (SL) which were measured biweekly. 6 birds were sampled out from each groups to analyse for blood sample. The results of the least squares means of body weight and body linear measurements followed an increasing trend across ages for all the groups. No significant ($P>0.05$) differences were obtained in dam line, sire control and dam control but all showed significantly ($P<0.05$) higher weight than sire line at 4, 6 and 8 weeks of age. There were no significant ($P>0.05$) differences in body length at 2 weeks but significant ($P<0.05$) differences were observed at week 4, 6, and 8 weeks. There was no significant ($P>0.05$) difference in the biochemical parameters observed except in Serum Alkaline phosphatase (SAP) where the sire control showed the highest value 69.00mg/dl. Genetic correlations obtained in this study revealed that serum alkaline phosphatase showed positive correlations with body weight at 8 week for the selected lines but negative correlations was shown in the control birds. The genetic correlations among alkaline phosphatase and other traits were both positive and negative though mostly positive with selected lines. It is therefore concluded that, genetics had significant effects on body weight and body linear measurements.

KEYWORDS: Growth, Body linear measurement, Serum Alkaline phosphatase

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INTRODUCTION

The performance of broiler birds is determined by its genotype and environmental factors (Boukwamp *et al.*, 1973; Edward and Denman, 1975). In animal breeding, it is imperative to determine breeding value with the objective of classifying the best individuals that will be the parents in the next generation, and quantifying its contribution to the genetic gain (Grosso *et al.*, 2010). In animal breeding, it is imperative to determine breeding value with the objective of classifying the best individuals that will be the parents in the next generation, and quantifying its contribution to the genetic gain (Grosso *et al.* 2010).

Evaluation of the performance of farm animals is carried out using various indices, especially the growth and development traits as well as body conformation traits. Linear measurements of body parts have heritable basis and have been identified to play a major role in the subsequent carcass yield of an animal (Falconer, 1989). Body parts such as keel length and width, body length, shank length are dependent on one another but when observed separately

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tend to make some facts known and provide ability to select superior individuals. A significant difference in serum alkaline phosphatase and blood haematological parameters of groups of birds could be of value to breeders for selection in early life. Serum alkaline phosphatase is an important enzyme in chicken which is majorly found in bones, kidney, liver, plasma and intestinal mucosa. It functions to help in absorption of protein, carbohydrate and fat (Das and Deb 2008). Alm El Dein *et al.* (2008) reported positive correlation between plasma alkaline phosphatase and body weight at 8 weeks and 12 weeks, age at sexual maturity and egg weight. This study was therefore designed to determine the growth traits and levels of alkaline phosphatase of male and female broiler lines in NAPRI, Shika, Zaria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Experimental Site

The research was carried out at the Poultry Research Unit of National Animal Production Research Institute (NAPRI) Shika, Zaria, Kaduna State. Shika lies between latitude 11° 12'N, longitude 7° 33'E and at altitude of 640m above sea level. The area falls within the Northern Guinea Savannah having an average annual rainfall of 1100mm. (Akpa and Jokthan, 1996).

Experimental Birds and Management

The birds used for this study comprised of 4 groups each of sire line, dam line, sire control and dam control line from a collapsed groups of Hubbard and Anak broiler birds in National Animal production Research Institute (NAPRI). Broiler starter mash with crude protein of 24.96% and energy of 2767.62 was given to the chicks at the first four weeks while broiler finisher mash with crude protein of 23.23 and energy of 2839.64 was given at the last four weeks of age. The same type of feed was given to all the groups. Water and feed were provided *ad-libitum*. All rations were formulated and mixed at the feed mill of the Institute (NAPRI) with appropriate composition shown in Table 1.

Data Collection and Analysis

The weight of individual birds and other body linear measurements were taken every two weeks for a period of eight weeks using a measuring scale in grams (g) and measuring tape in centimeter respectively. The body linear measurements considered were body length (BL), body girth (BG), thigh length (TL), keel length (KL), and shank length (SL) in (cm).

For the serum alkaline phosphatase (SAP), acetylcholine (Ach) and total protein (TP), blood sample was collected from 6 birds sampled from each group and allowed to coagulate and the serum was centrifuged for 16 hours to separate the serum. The serum was then deep frozen (-20°C) until analysis. Methods described by Bassey *et al.* (1946), George *et al.* (1961) and Abd El Azim (2012) were adopted for the analysis of (SAP), (Ach) and (TP) respectively.

Data on body weight, body linear measurements and blood parameter traits were analysed using General Linear Model procedures of SAS (2002). Significant differences among means were separated using Duncan's Multiple Range Test (Duncan 1955).

The genetic and phenotypic correlations between two traits were obtained by analysis of covariance using a procedure of statistical analysis system (SAS, 2002). The general formula for estimating correlation is as described by Falconer (1989).

$$r = \frac{COV_{xy}}{\sqrt{\sigma_x^2 \sigma_y^2}}$$

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Table 1: Composition of The Experimental Diets

Ingredients	PERCENTAGE	
	Broiler Starter	Broiler Finisher
Maize	45.00	52.00
Groundnut cake	30.00	30.00
Soyabean meal	15.00	10.00
Maize offal	4.60	2.50
Lime stone	3.00	1.50
Bone meal	1.50	3.00
Salt	0.30	0.30
Lysine	0.15	0.20
Methionine	0.15	0.20
Premix*	0.25	0.30
Total	100	100
Calculated analysis		
ME/Kal (Kg)	2767.62	2839.64
Crude Protein (%)	24.96	23.23
Crude Fibre (%)	3.82	3.45
Ether Extract (%)	5.16	5.22
Methionine	0.47	0.50
Methionine +	0.85	0.86
Cysteine		
Lysine	1.20	1.13
Calcium	1.75	1.74
Phosphorous available	0.90	0.89

*The premix used in this study supplied the following nutrients (Kg/diet): Vit A: 20,000,00, IU Vitamin E. 500 I, thiamin (B) 2,000mg, Riboflavin (B2) 3500mg, Vit (B3) 20000mg, Panthothenic acid (B5) 6,600ml, Pyridoxine (B6) 3600mg, Vitamin (B12) 20mg, folic acid 400mg, Vitamin 20000mg, Methionine 10,000mg, antioxidant 12.5g, Ca 18%, P.Mn 8.0g, Zn ug Iodine 0.12g.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONTable 2: The least squares means ($\pm$ SE) of body weight and body linear measurements of sire line, dam line, sire control and dam control at various ages

Age (weeks)	Line	N	BW (cm)	BL (cm)	BG (cm)	TL (cm)	KL (cm)	SL (cm)
2	Sire	84	112.00 $\pm$ 3.85 ^c	13.96 $\pm$ 1.22	10.54 $\pm$ 0.16 ^b	5.01 $\pm$ 0.28	4.13 $\pm$ 0.07 ^b	3.86 $\pm$ 0.06 ^b
	Dam	66	125.27 $\pm$ 4.34 ^b	12.55 $\pm$ 1.37	11.58 $\pm$ 0.18 ^a	5.11 $\pm$ 0.32	4.32 $\pm$ 0.08 ^b	3.82 $\pm$ 0.06 ^{bc}
	Sire control	62	139.11 $\pm$ 4.48 ^a	15.39 $\pm$ 1.42	11.63 $\pm$ 0.19 ^a	5.5 $\pm$ 0.33	4.62 $\pm$ 0.08 ^a	3.67 $\pm$ 0.07 ^c
	Dam control	56	127.75 $\pm$ 4.71 ^{ab}	12.70 $\pm$ 1.49	11.57 $\pm$ 0.19 ^a	5.02 $\pm$ 0.34	4.31 $\pm$ 0.08 ^b	4.02 $\pm$ 0.07 ^a
4	Sire	69	446.16 $\pm$ 18.45 ^b	14.41 $\pm$ 0.26 ^b	15.59 $\pm$ 0.93	6.38 $\pm$ 0.18 ^b	5.46 $\pm$ 0.39 ^b	4.60 $\pm$ 0.18 ^{ab}
	Dam	66	532.22 $\pm$ 18.86 ^a	16.36 $\pm$ 0.26 ^a	14.55 $\pm$ 0.95	7.77 $\pm$ 0.18 ^a	6.88 $\pm$ 0.40 ^a	4.86 $\pm$ 0.18 ^a
	Sire Control	58	558.22 $\pm$ 20.12 ^a	16.10 $\pm$ 0.28 ^a	15.21 $\pm$ 1.01	6.17 $\pm$ 0.20 ^b	5.76 $\pm$ 0.43 ^{ab}	4.49 $\pm$ 0.19 ^{ab}
	Dam Control	52	573.58 $\pm$ 21.25 ^a	15.61 $\pm$ 0.30 ^a	14.69 $\pm$ 1.07	6.33 $\pm$ 0.21 ^b	5.73 $\pm$ 0.45 ^{ab}	4.20 $\pm$ 0.21 ^b
6	Sire	64	1178.02 $\pm$ 58.59 ^b	20.91 $\pm$ 0.31 ^b	19.94 $\pm$ 0.38 ^b	9.21 $\pm$ 0.18	7.28 $\pm$ 0.14 ^b	4.63 $\pm$ 0.133 ^{ab}
	Dam	64	1386.60 $\pm$ 58.59 ^a	22.06 $\pm$ 0.31 ^a	20.36 $\pm$ 0.38 ^{ab}	9.13 $\pm$ 0.17	7.97 $\pm$ 0.14 ^a	4.36 $\pm$ 0.15 ^b
	Sire Control	48	1463.87 $\pm$ 67.60 ^a	22.06 $\pm$ 0.36 ^a	21.16 $\pm$ 0.44 ^a	9.10 $\pm$ 0.21	7.74 $\pm$ 0.17 ^a	4.91 $\pm$ 0.15 ^a
	Dam Control	50	1436.97 $\pm$ 64.38 ^a	21.86 $\pm$ 0.34 ^a	20.66 $\pm$ 0.42 ^{ab}	9.36 $\pm$ 0.20	7.48 $\pm$ 0.15 ^{ab}	4.47 $\pm$ 0.16 ^b
8	Sire	53	1349.79 $\pm$ 76.75 ^b	24.70 $\pm$ 0.37 ^a	20.86 $\pm$ 0.40	10.14 $\pm$ 0.44	8.13 $\pm$ 0.17 ^c	6.75 $\pm$ 0.13 ^a
	Dam	56	1988.86 $\pm$ 86.41 ^a	25.95 $\pm$ 0.42 ^{ab}	21.45 $\pm$ 0.45	10.86 $\pm$ 0.49	9.36 $\pm$ 0.19 ^b	6.45 $\pm$ 0.15 ^a
	Sire control	46	2005.98 $\pm$ 95.35 ^a	26.50 $\pm$ 0.46 ^a	21.96 $\pm$ 0.50	11.57 $\pm$ 0.54	10.93 $\pm$ 0.21 ^a	5.96 $\pm$ 0.16 ^b
	Dam Control	46	2038.07 $\pm$ 95.35 ^a	24.76 $\pm$ 0.46 ^b	22.02 $\pm$ 0.50	10.67 $\pm$ 0.54	9.44 $\pm$ 0.21 ^b	6.35 $\pm$ 0.16 ^{ab}

^{a,b,c} = Means with the same superscript within the same row for a particular parameter are not significantly ($P > 0.05$) different.

N=Number of the birds, BW=Body weight, BL= body length, BG=Body girth, TL= Thigh length, KL=keel length, SL=Shank length

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The results of least squares means ($\pm$ SE) for the body weight and body linear measurements in sire line, dam line, sire control and dam control broiler birds are presented in Table 2. The values for the body weight observed in this study were within the range of 1178.02–1349.79(g), 1386.60–1988.86(g), 1463.87–2005.98(g), 1436–2038.07(g), for sire line, dam line, sire control and dam control, respectively. The result of the body linear measurements obtained from this study revealed that lines showed significant ($P<0.05$) effects on body length from each other at 4, 6, and 8 weeks. No significant ($P>0.05$) effect on body length at 2 weeks was observed. The body length values obtained in this study from 2 to 8 weeks of age ranged within 12.55 to 26.509cm for all the groups.

The results of the mean body weight and body linear measurements followed an increasing trend across ages for all the groups and this is an indication of good performance in all the birds. This trend is supported by previous work of Pingel *et al.* (1990); and Essien and Adeyemi (1999), which suggested that age is a major determinant of growth and physiological development of animal. The significant difference obtained in the body weight at week 2 is an indication that selection processes could be carried out in early life of these birds. Mean while sire control showed best performance compared to others. Non significant difference observed in dam line, sire control and dam control in the body weight at 4, 6, and 8 week of age showed that line had no effect on these groups.

The values of the body weight observed in this study for sire line (1178.02 – 1349g), dam line (1386.60 – 1988.86g), sire control (1463.87 – 2005.98g) and dam control (1436 – 2038.07g) were all higher than the values obtained by Kabir *et al.* (2010) for Anak (948.61 – 1304) and Hubbard (904.46 – 1250) at 6 and 8 weeks of age. Differences in the results of body weights observed could be attributed to heterosis due to collapse of Anak and Hubbard broiler breeds, lines and breed effects; and/or environmental factors.

The significant difference obtained in the body linear measurement at various ages showed effects of line on these traits. However at week 4 and 8 no selection may be made on these lines on the bases of body girth and thigh length since no differences were posed by lines. The body length values obtained in this study from 2 to 8 weeks of age (12.55 to 26.50cm) for all the lines were higher than the values obtained by Kabir *et al.* (2010) for Anak and Hubbard (3.30 to 9.20cm). These differences are also attributed to line and breed effect. The values obtained for shank length (4.3 – 5.88cm) for all the lines were higher than that obtained by Kabir *et al.* (2010) at 2 and 4 weeks for Anak and Hubbard (3.48 – 5.44cm) though agreed with that of Kabir *et al.* (2010) at 6 and 8 weeks of age. The values for shank length were lower at 6 and 8 weeks of age for all lines than that obtained by Kabir *et al.* (2010) for Anak and Hubbard. These differences are as a result of heterosis (hybrid vigour from gene action and interaction) due to the collapse of Anak and Hubbard broiler breeds.

Table 3: The least squares means ($\pm$ SE) of the Serum Alkaline phosphatase and blood biochemistry of sire line, dam line, sire control and dam control

Traits	Sire line	Dam line	Sire control	Dam control
SAP(mg/dl)	64.67 $\pm$ 2.830 ^b	63.33 $\pm$ 2.830 ^b	69.00 $\pm$ 2.830 ^a	63.17 $\pm$ 2.830 ^b
Ach(mg/dl)	21.50 $\pm$ 1.600	20.83 $\pm$ 1.610	21.33 $\pm$ 1.600	19.17 $\pm$ 1.610
TP(mg/dl)	7.05 $\pm$ 0.880	6.83 $\pm$ 0.880	7.08 $\pm$ 0.880	6.92 $\pm$ 0.880

^{a,b,c} = Means with the same superscript within the same row for a particular parameter are not significantly ($P>0.05$) different.

SAP=Serum Alkaline phosphatase, Ach=Acetylcholine esterase, TP=Total Protein,

The result of the least squares means for the biochemical and haematological parameters for sire line, dam line, sire control and dam control is presented in Table 3. The values of the serum alkaline phosphatase (SAP) obtained in this study was 64.67 μ /l for sire line, 63.33 μ /l for dam line, 69.00 μ /l for sire control and 63.17 μ /l for dam control. The values for Acetylcholine esterase (Ach) ranged from 19.17 to 21.50mg/dl for all the lines. The values for total protein (TP) also ranged from 6.83 to 7.08mg/dl for all the lines. There was no significant ($P>0.05$) difference in the biochemical parameters observed except in SAP where the sire control showed the highest value. The significant

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difference obtained in serum alkaline phosphatase showed that there is line effect of serum alkaline phosphatase and this could pose advantage of better performance in terms of body weight. The values of TP ranged from 6.83 to 7.08mg/dl and SAP ranged from 63.17 to 64.67 μ /l and these disagreed with the value obtained by Abd El Azim (2012) for TP (4.60) and SAP (143), respectively. The differences could be due to breed and environmental effects.

Table 4: The genetic correlation of serum alkaline phosphatase with 8 week body weight and body length of sire line, dam line, Sire control and dam control
SAP=Serum Alkaline phosphatase

Traits	Sire line	Dam Line	Sire control	Dam control
SAP and Weight at 8 week of age	0.412	0.499	-0.553	0.894
SAP and Body length at 8 week of age	-0.140	-0.589	–	–
Body weight and length at 8 week of age	0.770	0.400	-0.473	-0.824

Table 5: The phenotypic correlation coefficient of serum alkaline phosphatase with 8 week body weight and body length of sire line, dam line, Sire control and dam control
SAP=Serum Alkaline phosphatase

Traits	Sire line	Dam Line	Sire control	Dam control
SAP and Weight at 8 week of age	0.408	0.484	-0.463	-0.887
SAP and Body length at 8 week of age	-0.128	-0.538	-0.707	-0.867
Body weight and length at 8 week of age	0.713	0.419	-0.299	-0.719

The results of the genetic and phenotypic correlation coefficients of serum alkaline phosphatase with 8 week body weight and body length of sire line, dam line, sire control and dam control are presented in Table 3 and 4. The results of this study revealed that in sire and dam line, genetic and phenotypic correlation between serum alkaline phosphatase and body weight was high and positive and ranged from 0.400 to 0.499. These results suggest strong interrelationship between these traits and that selection for the improvement of one trait will lead to improvement in other traits desired. This disagreed with the result of Strivastava *et al.* (2004) which showed moderate and significant correlation of alkaline phosphatase with body weight. The genetic and phenotypic correlation between serum alkaline phosphatase and body length were all negative for all the groups even though they ranged from low to high (-0.128 to -0.887). The genetic and phenotypic correlations of body weight were positive and high with selected lines (sire and dam) ranging from 0.400 to 0.770 but negative with sire control and dam control.

CONCLUSION

The increasing order obtained in the results of body weight and body linear measurements with age of the birds implies that age is a determinant of body growth and that birds showed good performance and that genetics had significant effects on body weight and body linear measurements in the birds. The significant differences obtained in most of the measured traits and SAP in the groups are indications of line effects. High and positive genetic and phenotypic correlations obtained between alkaline phosphatase and body weight and also between body length are indications of linkage and pleiotropy effects. Negative correlations observed in this study indicate no linkage among the traits considered and selection for those traits will lead to no improvement in others.

Therefore for selection purposes, Serum Alkaline phosphatase (SAP) is recommended as a marker for selection for improved growth traits.

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